

Synthesis, structure and properties of a mononuclear nickel(II) acetate complex containing a tetradentate *N*-donor Schiff base

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Abstract : One hexacoordinated mononuclear compound of the type $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})]\text{PF}_6$ (**1**) [L = *N,N'*-(bis(pyridine-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,4-butanediamine] has been synthesized and characterized by physico-chemical and spectroscopic methods. Single crystal X-ray structural analysis shows that nickel(II) center in **1** adopts a distorted octahedral geometry bound by four N atoms of L and two O atoms of an acetate in chelating fashions. In crystalline state, mononuclear units in **1** are engaged in weak cooperative intermolecular C-H...O hydrogen bonds and $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions affording to a 2D sheet structure. Compound **1** is thermally stable up to 251 °C and displays $^1(\pi\text{-}\pi^*)$ fluorescence at room temperature in DMF solution.

Keywords : Nickel(II) acetate, Schiff base, synthesis, X-ray structure, luminescence.

Introduction

The study of mono-, di-, and polynuclear complexes of nickel(II) has been the center of current research because of their interesting synthetic, structural, spectroscopic, magnetic and optoelectronic features¹⁻⁵. The essential prerequisites for such research are the judicious choice⁶ of organic spacers and inorganic/organic terminals/bridges that may lead to directed molecular properties. Recently, we are interested⁷⁻¹¹ in the construction of different coordination molecules through variation of ligand backbones and metal ion coordination environments; in this regard, Schiff base spacers and pseudohalide terminals/bridges have been widely used. Schiff bases^{12,13} are useful chelators because of their ease of preparation, structural varieties, varied denticities and subtle steric and/or electronic control on their frameworks. Carboxylate like acetate¹⁴⁻²⁰ is known to be efficient bridging unit allowing magnetic exchanges in accordance with its specific coordination motifs and bond parameters of the bridging zone in several paramagnetic transition metal complexes leading to molecule-based magnets. Earlier we reported^{16,18} some mono- and dinuclear copper(II) acetate complexes of 2,2'-dipyridylamine with interesting molecular and crystalline architectures coupled with ferro-

magnetic and luminescent properties. The present work stems from our interest to build new molecular and crystalline aggregates of nickel(II) in combination with a Schiff base, *N,N'*-(bis(pyridine-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,4-butanediamine (L; Scheme 1) and acetate. Successfully, we have isolated a mononuclear complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})]\text{PF}_6$ (**1**). The details of synthesis, characterization, structure and properties of this compound are described below.

Scheme 1. $\text{N}^{\text{P}}, \text{N}^{\text{I}}, \text{N}^{\text{I}}, \text{N}^{\text{P}}$ donor set of L.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

Compound **1** was obtained in good yield using one-pot synthesis of a 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, tetradentate Schiff base (L) and KPF_6 in MeOH solution at room temperature. The corresponding

molar ratio was expected to yield either a mononuclear compound $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})](\text{PF}_6)$ (**I**) with chelating acetate moiety or a diacetate bridged dinuclear entity $[(\text{L})\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{Ni}(\text{L})](\text{PF}_6)_2$ (**II**) (see Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Expected compounds with 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of the building units.

The air-stable moisture-insensitive compound **1** is crystalline and soluble in a range of common organic solvents such as MeOH, EtOH, MeCN, DMF and DMSO but is insoluble in H_2O . In DMF solution, **1** shows conductivity value (Experimental) corresponding to 1 : 1 electrolytic behavior²¹. Room-temperature solid-phase magnetic susceptibility measurement shows that **1** has magnetic moment value 2.85 BM close to the spin-only ($S = 1$) value (2.82 BM) expected from discrete and magnetically non-coupled mononuclear $3d^8$ ion.

Crystal structure of **1** :

ORTEP plot with atom numbering scheme of **1** is shown in Fig. 1. Selected bond lengths and angles pertaining to the coordination spheres are set in Table 1. Structural analysis reveals that the asymmetric unit consists of $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})]\text{PF}_6$ (Fig. 1a). The coordination polyhedron around nickel(II) is best described as a distorted octahedron with an NiN_4O_2 chromophore. Two O atoms (O1 and O2) of chelated acetate unit and one pyridine N atom (N1) and one imine N atom (N3) of the Schiff base (L) occupy the equatorial positions while re-

Fig. 1. (a) An ORTEP diagram of $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})]^{1+}$ in **1** with atom numbering schemes and 30% thermal ellipsoid probability for all non hydrogen atoms and (b) a view of 2D sheet structure in **1** formed through $\text{C}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ and $\pi\cdots\pi$ interactions.

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles ($^\circ$) for **1**

Bond distances		Bond angles	
Ni1-N1	2.0648(12)	N4-Ni1-N2	170.78(5)
Ni1-N2	2.0606(12)	N3-Ni1-O1	163.61(4)
Ni1-N3	2.0505(12)	N1-Ni1-O2	152.79(4)
Ni1-N4	2.0586(12)	N2-Ni1-N1	79.88(5)
Ni1-O1	2.0883(10)	N3-Ni1-N2	91.84(5)
Ni1-O2	2.1821(10)	N3-Ni1-N4	79.14(5)
		O1-Ni1-O2	61.89(4)

maining pyridine N (N4) and imine N (N2) atoms of L are placed at the axial positions. The degrees of distortion of the coordination spheres are reflected in the *cisoid* [61.89(4)–103.58°] and the *transoid* [152.79(4)–170.78(5)°] angles. The metal center is displaced from the mean equatorial plane by 0.012 Å. The average values of Ni–N(L) and Ni–O(acetate) bond distances are 1.936 Å and 1.928 Å, respectively as expected¹⁹. The tetradentate ligand is twisted around the nickel(II) center such that the two planes containing the unsaturated chelate rings (Ni1, N1, C5, C6, N2) and (Ni1, N3, C17, C24, N4) are inclined at 69.36° to each other. The butylenic arm of L is to some extent puckered.

In crystalline state, mononuclear units in **1** are engaged in weak cooperative intermolecular C–H···O hydrogen bonds and $\pi\cdots\pi$ interaction giving rise to a 2D sheet structure (Table 2; Fig. 1b).

Thermal behavior :

To examine thermal stability of **1**, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was made between 40 to 700 °C in a static atmosphere of nitrogen. TGA analysis (Fig. 2) indicates that **1** is stable up to 251 °C and decomposes gradually in three successive steps in the temperature range 251–552 °C with the release of acetate and L units (calcd. : 70.02%, obsd. : 73.82%). In summary, thermogravimetric analysis shows that compound **1** has reasonable thermal stability.

Luminescence property :

The photoluminescence behaviours of the free ligand (L) and its compound (**1**) are examined in DMF solutions. The nature of the emission spectra of L and **1** is depicted in Fig. 3. Upon photo-excitation at the corresponding absorption band (280 nm) in DMF solution, L exhibits a broad fluorescent emission centered at 385 nm,

Table 2. Hydrogen bond parameters (Å, °) for **1**

D–H···A	D–H	H···A	D···A	D–H···A
C15–H15A···O1 ^a	0.99	2.60	3.4721(18)	147
C21–H21···F3 ^b	0.95	2.53	3.375(2)	148
$\pi\cdots\pi$ interaction parameters (Å, °)				
Cg–Cg	Cg–Cg distance	Dihedral angle (i,j)	Perpendicular distances between baricentres (i,j)	Slippage
Cg(2)···Cg(2) ^c	4.2512(10)	0	3.6896(7)	2.112
Symmetry code : (a) 1/2+x, 1/2-y, 1/2+z; (b) 1-x, -y, 2-z; (c) 1-x, -y, 1-z. Cg(2) : N(4)→C(24)→C(25)→C(26)→C(27)→C(28).				

Spectroscopic studies :

In IR spectrum, the characteristic stretching vibrations of acetate are seen as strong $\nu_{as}(\text{COO}^-)$, $\nu_s(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\delta(\text{OCO})$ absorptions at 1654, 1570, 1538 cm^{-1} , at 1345 cm^{-1} and at 799 cm^{-1} , respectively which indicates oxygen coordination of carboxylate group¹³. The metal bound Schiff base (L) in **1** shows $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ stretching frequencies²² at 1625 and 1591 cm^{-1} . The presence of hexafluorophosphate stretches at 846 and 557 cm^{-1} is noticed reflecting counter anionic view²² with no metal coordination. DMF solution of **1** exhibits two d-d bands at 555 and 893 nm representing spin-allowed ${}^3T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ and ${}^3T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ transitions, respectively and the shoulder at 791 nm originating from spin-forbidden ${}^1E_g \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ transition, frequently observed in nickel(II) octahedral complexes²³. Additionally, two ligand based transitions at 320 and 277 nm are found.

whereas **1** shows more intense photoluminescence with main emission at *ca.* 387 nm (Fig. 3). The maximum emission energy of the complex as well as the ligand is very similar indicating emission behavior of the ligand remains almost unchanged upon coordination. The luminescence behavior in **1** may be attributed^{24–26} to the intraligand ${}^1(\pi-\pi^*)$ emission. The increase in luminous intensity value of the complex as compared to that of the free ligand (L) may presumably be due to the increase in conformational rigidity²⁶ of the ligand upon coordination.

Conclusion :

We are able to isolate and X-ray crystallographically characterize one mononuclear nickel(II) acetate complex in combination with a tetradentate Schiff base prepared through single-pot reactions of the molecular building units in preassigned molar ratio. The compound is thermally stable and shows good luminescence property.

Fig. 2. Thermal behaviour of 1.

Fig. 3. Emission spectra of L and 1 (fluorescence in DMF solutions at room temperature).

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity 2-benzoylpyridine (Lancaster, UK), butane-1,4-diamine (Lancaster, UK), nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate (E. Merck, India) and potassium hexafluorophosphate (Fluka, Germany) were purchased from respective concerns and were used as received. All other chemicals and solvents used were AR grade and used as received. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air. Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were done using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectrum (KBr

discs, $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) was recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. Molar conductance was measured using a Systronics conductivity meter where the cell constant was calibrated with 0.01 M KCl solution and dry DMF was used as solvent. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility was measured on a CAHN electrobalance 7550 with $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as a reference and diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants²⁷. Thermal behavior was investigated with a Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DT analyzer heated from $30\text{--}850\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under nitrogen. Ground state absorption and steady-state fluorescence measurements (in DMF) were made with a Shimadzu model UV-2450 UV-Vis spectrophotometer and a Hitachi model F-4010 spectrofluorimeter,

Preparation of Schiff base :

The Schiff base (L) was prepared following reported methods¹³.

Preparation of the complex :

The complex 1 was prepared from acetate salt of nickel(II) with a 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of metal salt, Schiff base and counter anion. The typical synthesis is described below.

Synthesis of $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})]\text{PF}_6$ (1) : A faint yellow methanolic solution (15 ml) of L (0.418 g, 1 mmol) was added dropwise to a green methanolic solution (15 ml) of $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.248 g, 1 mmol). To this resulting yellowish-green solution, a methanolic solution (30

ml) of KPF_6 (0.184 g, 1 mmol) was added slowly. The final solution was filtered and left for slow evaporation in air at room temperature. After 7 days fine brown micro-crystalline product of **1** that separated, was washed with toluene and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield 0.49 g (72%) (Found : C, 52.7; H, 4.3; N, 8.1. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{PF}_6\text{Ni}$ (**1**) : C, 52.9; H, 4.3; N, 8.2%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ 1625, 1595; $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ 1654, 1570, 1538; $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$ 1345; $\delta(\text{OCO})$ 799; $\nu(\text{PF}_6)$ 846, 557; Λ_{M} (DMF, $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) : 130; UV-Vis in DMF (λ , nm) : 893, 791, 555, 320, 277; μ_{eff} : 2.85 BM.

X-Ray crystallographic analysis :

An appropriate single crystal of **1** was mounted on a Bruker SMART APEX II CCD area detector diffractometer at 100(2) K using graphite monochromated Mo- $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Intensity data of **1** were reduced using SAINT²⁸ and the empirical absorption corrections were performed with SADABS program²⁹. The structure was solved by SHELXS-97³⁰ and refined by full-matrix least-square methods based on $|F|^2$ using SHELXL-97³⁰. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atoms were placed in calculated positions and constrained to ride on their parent atoms. All the calculations were carried out using PLATON³¹ and X-Seed³² programs. The crystallographic data for the complex **1** are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Crystallographic data for **1**

Crystallographic parameter	1
Chemical formula	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{PF}_6\text{Ni}$
Formula mass	681.25
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P21/n
Crystal size (mm^3)	$0.13 \times 0.25 \times 0.25$
D(cal) (g cm^{-3})	1.543
<i>a</i> (\AA)	9.6071(9)
<i>b</i> (\AA)	23.895(2)
<i>c</i> (\AA)	13.5572(13)
β ($^\circ$)	109.537(1)
Unit cell volume (\AA^3)	2933.0(5)
Temperature (K)	100(2)
<i>F</i> (000)	1400
No. of formula units per unit cell, <i>Z</i>	4
Absorption coefficient, μ (mm^{-1})	0.790
θ range for data collection ($^\circ$)	1.7 to 28.09

Table-3 (contd.)

<i>h/k/l</i>	-12,12/-31,31/-17,17
T_{min} and T_{max}	0.8269 and 0.9077
No. of reflections measured	32827
No. of independent reflections	6631
Data/restraints/parameters	6631/0/398
R_{int}	0.025
Final R_1 values ($I > 2\sigma(I)$)	0.0269
Final $wR(F^2)$ values ($I > 2\sigma(I)$)	0.0647
Final R_1 values (all data)	0.0322
Final $wR(F^2)$ values (all data)	0.0677
Goodness of fit on F^2	1.044
Largest peak and hole ($\text{e}\text{\AA}^{-3}$)	0.336 and -0.323
$R = \Sigma F_o - F_c /\Sigma F_o $, $wR = [\Sigma w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2/\Sigma w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$, calcd. $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0300P)^2 + 1.5237P]$; where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.	

Supplementary materials :

Crystallographic data for the structural analyses have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC No. 893157 for **1**). Copies of this information can be obtained free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : 44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

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